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Budol Culture:

***The Effects of TikTok Media Influencers' Characteristics and Marketing
Techniques on Consumers' Purchasing Decisions***

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28 August 2024

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Acceptance Page:

This paper prepared by **CLARISSE ANGELINE ROSARIO** with the title: “**Budol Culture: The Effects of TikTok Media Influencers’ Characteristics and Marketing Techniques on Consumers’ Purchasing Decisions**” is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Information and Communication Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Course.

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Biographical Sketch

Clarisse Angeline P. Rosario, pursued the Bachelor of Arts in Multimedia Studies at the University of the Philippines Open University. Hailing from Rodriguez, Rizal, she is the third of eight siblings. She has demonstrated a strong commitment to academic excellence, having achieved notable recognition in high school and striving for an academic excellence award in her current college studies.

In addition to her academic pursuits, she also actively works as an executive virtual assistant and engages in social media content creation and graphic design for small businesses. Her professional experience enhances her academic background, offering a diverse skill set that supports both her research and creative work. She aims to combine academic excellence with practical experience to become a dedicated and resourceful professional in multimedia studies.

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Abstract

This study examined the impact of influencer characteristics and techniques on purchasing decisions among senior Bachelor of Arts in Multimedia Studies students at the University of the Philippines Open University. Thirty participants shared their experiences through online surveys distributed via Facebook, covering aspects such as demographics, shopping behavior, influencer traits, and consumer experiences. The data were analyzed using quantitative-descriptive methods. The results indicated that authenticity, product knowledge, and engaging content are the most valued characteristics of TikTok influencers among the respondents, while over-promotion and a lack of transparency serve as significant deterrents affecting their purchasing decisions. Effective influencer techniques identified include demonstrating product use and providing honest reviews, while generic content and hidden sponsorships were considered less effective. The findings also revealed that when engaging in online shopping, consumers prioritize price, necessity, and product quality. When respondents were asked about their actions following unsatisfactory purchases, common responses included leaving negative reviews or requesting refunds. These insights offer valuable guidance for businesses, influencers, and consumers to enhance marketing strategies and make informed purchasing decisions.

CHAPTER 1

RATIONALE AND BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Introduction

Apart from serving as a platform for interpersonal contact and social engagement, social media is also utilized for information dissemination, for raising brand awareness for goods and services, and for attracting new customers while retaining current ones (Varghese & Agrawal, 2021). Similar to traditional marketing, such as print, radio, and television advertisements, in social media marketing, endorsements play a significant role in achieving a company's good reputation and business goals (Lim et al., 2017). Social media influencers assume the role of third-party endorsers responsible for sharing product information, boosting customer engagement, and promoting products to their online followers across different platforms.

According to Bogner et al. (2019), influencer marketing is the art and science of enlisting individuals with online influence to propagate a particular trend and reach its intended audience through sponsored content. They also stated that influencer marketing is similar to advertising with celebrities, wherein it is believed that people easily trust those whom they admire and want to be. Seeing an influencer using or wearing a product resonates with the social identity aspect, as consumers feel the desire to align and conform their identity with those they admire (Barcelona et al., 2022). On the other hand, according to the data provided by an

influencer marketing platform, 92% of consumers trust influencers more than celebrity endorsements (Weinswig, 2016). According to Dinh and Lee's study from 2021, one of the key elements influencing consumers' purchasing intentions for things that influencers recommend is their desire to emulate them.

TikTok as a social media and advertising platform

Users of the social media site TikTok can create and share short movies with information, using it as a medium for enjoyment (Saputro et al., 2023). Moreover, TikTok was also regarded as one of the major online platforms that blurred the line between content and commerce, with some TikTok influencers entertaining and selling products to their audiences (Yang et al., 2021). The platform offers various features that expand its function as an effective marketplace, allowing users to buy and sell products within the app.

One of the most prominent features of the platform is its complex algorithmic system, which allows it to showcase the most interesting content tailored to users' preferences through the "For You Page" (FYP). The algorithm on TikTok is effective at predicting videos that a user might like. It can determine how much each user values various videos or products, recognize repeat buyers, and then present them with additional films featuring items they should purchase (Ren et al., 2021). By giving them access to a wider and more varied audience, these elements of the platform have helped advertisers and marketers increase their chances of driving sales (Later, n.d.).

In making TikTok ads effective, influencers play a crucial role. These video creators capture viewers' attention, especially when there is trust and a perceived connection with the influencer. TikTok influencers use the platform's entertaining features to make products and brands more interesting. People tend to like product reviews from influencers more than traditional ads and commercials because they seem genuine and trustworthy (Grafström et al., 2018). Thus, businesses send their products for testing to influencers, paying them for reviews in an effort to increase consumer interest in and exposure to their offerings.

The "budol" culture is one of the trends on the TikTok app. "Budol" is a Filipino word that denotes deception or trickery. Then the word "budol" began to mean purchasing goods that are being advertised on social media or giving in to peer pressure to make impulsive or unintended purchases as online shopping gained popularity in the Philippines. Gen Z was known to be one of the perpetrators of using the word to mean the latter.

According to TikTok's creative center and analytics, 67% of the audience within the platform, with ages ranging from 18 to 24 years old, or Gen Z, uses the hashtag #budol or #budolfinds (Mirano, 2023). Statistics also showed that 55% of TikTok users have purchased something after seeing it on the app and 50% after watching TikTok live (West, 2023). Gen Z has emerged as one of the main target demographics for businesses on social media platforms due to their increased activity on these platforms, especially TikTok. They are also more susceptible to persuasion and impulsive buying (Ye et al., 2021). This study will try to understand the impact of influencer marketing on the consumer behavior of Gen Z, particularly

the 4th year Bachelor of Arts in Multimedia Studies (BAMS) students of the University of the Philippines Open University (UPOU) as of the school year 2023-2024

Statement of the Problem

This study shall specifically answer the following questions:

- 1) What are the characteristics of a TikTok media influencer that a consumer looks for to be convinced to buy or consume a product?
- 2) What are the influencer characteristics that caused the consumer not to buy or consume a product?
- 3) Which techniques used by TikTok media influencers are effective in persuading consumers to purchase a product?
- 4) Which techniques used by TikTok media influencers are ineffective in persuading consumers to purchase a product?

Objectives of the Study

This study aims to determine the impact of an influencer's marketing characteristics on consumers' behavior. Specifically, it shall

- 1) Identify the characteristics of a TikTok media influencer that can convince a consumer to buy or consume a product.
- 2) Identify the characteristics of a TikTok media influencer that caused a consumer to not buy a product.
- 3) Identify which techniques used by TikTok media influencers are effective in persuading consumers to purchase a product.
- 4) Identify which techniques used by TikTok media influencers are ineffective in

persuading consumers to purchase a product.

The Significance of the Study

The results of the study can be of used to the following members of the online community:

Online Shoppers and Consumers: This can serve as a guide for online shoppers to make well-informed purchasing decisions by increasing awareness about the marketing and persuasion strategies employed by TikTok media influencers.

TikTok Media Influencers and Business Owners: can provide valuable insights into the factors that impact consumers' purchasing decisions, thus helping develop other effective online marketing strategies.

Scope and Limitations of the Study

The participants of this study are the senior or fourth-year BAMS students at the UPOU as of the school year 2023-2024. The findings of this study may be true only to this particular group of respondents.

CHAPTER 2

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

TikTok Influencers' Characteristics and Credibility

Influencers have the power to influence the purchasing process and decisions of their followers through several factors, such as their knowledge, authority, persuasion ability, and relationship with the followers. They were considered to be part of both internal and external factors affecting consumer behavior (Tram, 2022). According to Solomon et al. (2019), influencers use three different psychological variables to generate their social impact. These powers, as classified by Solomon et al. (2019), include referral power, wherein followers admire and emulate the influencer's behavior. Information power, where followers perceive the influencer as a source of valuable information and act in accordance. Finally, there is expert power, where followers view influencers as experts whom they trust.

Furthermore, according to Kanaveedu and Kalapurackal (2022), influencer marketing has the power to persuade, which frequently results in the audience's desire to make a purchase. Petty & Cacioppo (1981) defined the theory of persuasion as a process of changing someone's attitude and behavior. The elaboration likelihood model of persuasion suggests two modes of persuasion, namely the central route, where elaboration is more likely to occur as the recipient emphasizes the message's value similarities with themselves, and the peripheral route, where elaboration is less likely and the recipient focuses on the sender's attractiveness (Nilsson et al., 2023). Consumers frequently characterize influencers

depending on their traits when it comes to influencer marketing. Customers' behavioral intentions, especially their purchase intents, are subsequently influenced by these perceived characterizations (Masuda et al., 2022).

According to the study by Kurdi et al. (2022), factors like perceived communication, respect, and trustworthiness significantly impact consumers' intentions to purchase products recommended by influencers through advertising videos. The results also demonstrated that the relatability and attractiveness of the source supported the idea that consumers' purchase intentions are influenced by the traits and qualities of influencers. Therefore, the persuasive abilities and attributes of influencers play a significant role in shaping consumers' decisions to make a purchase.

Budol Culture and Impulse Buying Behavior

TikTok, a social media platform, has gained popularity for its unique algorithm. This has led businesses to view the platform as an ideal place to refocus their marketing efforts (Barcelona et al., 2022) The “budol” culture is one of the trends that arise on the platform, wherein users or consumers are persuaded by someone into buying anything unplanned or impulsive. According to Hawkins Stern's Impulse Buying Theory, consumers often indulge in spontaneous purchasing actions influenced by external factors. The theory further posits that marketers can persuade consumers to exceed their initial purchase intentions (Ankita, 2022).

Stern identifies four categories of impulse buying -- pure impulse buying,

reminded impulsive buying, planned impulse buying, and suggested impulse buying. Pure impulse buying involves deviating from the regular purchasing pattern by acquiring items not initially planned or listed. Reminded impulsive buying happens when a product prompts customers to realize they need it when they see it in the store. While planned impulse buying happens when customers believe a product is necessary but are unsure of its specifications. On the other hand, suggested impulse buying refers to customers who impulsively decide to buy a product upon seeing it. These four categories are frequently influenced by sales promotions and discounted prices (Barcelona et al., 2022).

The impulse buying theory has provided a valuable outlook on consumers' purchasing decisions, particularly in the present-day context. It has also been considered essential in understanding the specific impulsive buying patterns observed among TikTok users and the contributing factors to such impulsive behavior.

Conceptual Framework

The diagram shows that the independent variable, which includes factors such as influencers' persuasion ability, credibility, and perceived characteristics, significantly affects the dependent variable, which is the consumers' purchasing decisions. In this study, perceived characteristics include the following: authenticity, physical attractiveness, social media status and presence, expertise in the product category, transparency about sponsorship, fun and outgoing personalities, engaging and relatable content, positive reputation, and credibility. It also includes the

characteristics that deter consumers from purchasing such as lack of authenticity, perceived insincerity, small social media presence, over-promoting products, poor understanding of the product, lack of transparency, and negative reputation.

Meanwhile, the influencer techniques include demonstrating the product use, providing honest reviews, interactive content, limited-time offers or discounts, collaborations with other influencers, and behind-the-scenes content. Techniques that deter consumers include excessive promotion, generic or unoriginal content, hidden sponsorship, and overly scripted content.

Operational Definition of Terms

Budol Culture - a social media trend where people make unplanned purchases because someone has influenced or persuaded them to purchase a product or service.

Consumer - A person who buys a product or service for personal use or other reasons.

Consumer Behavior - the actions and decisions made by individuals when choosing, purchasing, and disposing of a product or service.

Influencer Marketing - the use of social media influencers to promote or endorse products and services.

Purchasing Decision - a decision process where consumers make a final decision about what product or service to purchase.

Purchase Intention - an individual's conscious intention to proceed with a purchase.

Social Media Influencers - Social media users who have access to a large audience and can persuade others through information sharing.

TikTok - a social media platform that allows users to make short videos using its features.

CHAPTER 3

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Approach

For this study, the quantitative descriptive research approach, which involves the collection of numerical data to examine trends and averages (Bhandari, 2023) was used. This approach allowed the collection and analysis of data that described the traits and consumer behaviors of target participants towards TikTok media influencers.

Research Instrument

The researcher created an online survey questionnaire using Google Forms. The questionnaire has questions about the participants' demographic background and shopping experience on TikTok. Additionally, the Likert scale statements and open-ended questions were included to measure the respondents' perceptions.

The questionnaire was distributed to intended research participants by doing an open call on a Facebook page where target participants are members or followers. The link to the questionnaire was also posted on the Facebook pages. The data collection started in the first week and ended in the second week of the second trimester of the academic year 2023-2024.

Respondents and Locale of the Study

The participants were senior or fourth-year students under the BAMS degree program as of SY 2023-2024 and were living in the Philippines. The majority of them were active users of social media and belonged to Generation Z. The target respondents were 30% of the total 101 fourth year students of BAMS.

Sampling Procedure

The volunteer sampling technique was employed in this study. It is where participants, who met the criteria, voluntarily chose to engage in a study through self-selection or volunteering. The researcher designed and developed advertising material, which was posted on the UPOU BAMS Facebook page. To increase the study's reach, respondents who have finished the survey were requested to refer to other potential participants.

Advertisement sample

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher created an advertising post on the UPOU BAMS Facebook page to call for participants. Those who met the criteria as target respondents and volunteered to participate by completing the survey constituted the participants of the study. The data collection started in the first week and ended in the second week of the second trimester of the academic year 2023-2024.

Data Analysis

The researcher used descriptive data analysis, specifically frequency, percentages, and computations of means. The researcher looked into the frequency distribution—which describes the frequency at which each value or variable occurs—central tendency, which calculates the data set's mean, median, and mode, and variability, which calculates the dispersion of values within the dataset—to characterize and condense the key features of a dataset while refraining from extrapolating or drawing conclusions from the data itself (Bhandari, 2023). This descriptive data analysis helps get a general understanding of the data.

Quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, including means, medians, and standard deviations, to identify trends and patterns. Inferential statistics, such as correlation and regression analyses, may also be used to explore relationships between variables.

CHAPTER 4

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Section 1: The Socio-demographic Profile of Respondents

Understanding the diversity of the sample and how various aspects, like age, gender, and work status, contribute to the research findings is made possible by analyzing the demographics of the respondents. Thirty UPOU BAMS students, who are in their senior or fourth year, are the study's target population.

1.1 Age

Figure 1.1 *Age of Respondents*

The respondents were categorized into four age groups: 18-22; 23-27; 28-32; and 32 and above. Figure 1.1 showed that most respondents (66.7%) are aged 18-22, suggesting a predominantly younger sample, while the remaining 33.3% are in the 23-27 range. Given this distribution, the survey results will primarily reflect the perspectives of younger individuals.

1.2 Age

Figure 1.1 Sex of Respondents

As shown in Figure 1.2, most respondents (70%) are female, while 30% are male. The dominance in the number of female respondents may suggest that females are more inclined to shop online compared to males. A study conducted by Precti and Kashyap (2015) revealed that females have a more positive attitude towards online purchasing and are more inclined to make frequent online purchases than their male counterparts.

1.3 Employment Status

Figure 1.3 Employment Status of the Respondents

In terms of employment status, Figure 1.3 showed that almost three-fourths of the respondents are full-time students (73.3%), while the rest are either part-time workers (13.3%) or full-time workers (13.3%).

Section 2: Customer Shopping Behavior

This section analyzes the data gathered on how often respondents shop on TikTok, their reasons for buying via TikTok, and their average monthly spending on the said platform.

2.1 Frequency of Shopping on TikTok

Figure 2.1 Respondents' Shopping Frequency on TikTok

Figure 2.1 showed that almost one-half of the respondents (48.7%) shop on TikTok once a month. This is followed by 30% (9 respondents) who shop 3–4 times a month. Additionally, 10% (3 respondents) shop twice a week, 6.7% (2 respondents) shop once a week, and another 6.7% (2 respondents) shop daily.

2.2 Reasons for Buying via TikTok

Figure 2.2 Reasons for Purchasing via TikTok Among Respondents

The respondents were asked to select their reasons for buying on TikTok from a list, with the option to choose more than one. Figure 2.2 showed that the most cited reasons were unique and trending products (56.7%) and fast delivery (56.7%), followed by ease of use (53.3%). Other reasons included curiosity and impulse buying (40%), entertainment and engagement (33.3%), limited-time discounts and promotions (30%), influencer recommendations (26.7%), and social proof (23.3%).

2.3 The Average Amount Spent in the TikTok Shop per Month

Figure 2.3 Average Spending of Respondents in TikTok Shops per Month.

As shown in Figure 2.3, 46.7% of the respondents spent PHP 200.00 or below on TikTok per month. This suggests that a significant portion of users were either more cautious with their spending or had limited budgets. Furthermore, over 36.7% of respondents spend between PHP 201.00 and PHP 500.00 per month, indicating moderate spending. On the other hand, a smaller group of respondents (10%) are willing to spend significantly more, with an average spending of PHP 501.00 to 1000.00 per month. Lastly, 6.7% of respondents are heavy users, spending an average of PHP 1,000.00 or more, indicating a significant niche market with substantial spending power. Since more consumers spend less per month, the data suggests that offering a considerable range of affordable products on the platform could attract a significant segment of consumers who spend PHP 200.00 or below in TikTok shops.

2.4 Items Consumers Usually Buy on TikTok

Figure 2.4 Items Respondents Buy on TikTok.

Figure 2.4 showed that all 30 respondents purchased fashion and clothing items on TikTok. Additionally, 73.3% of them also purchased skincare and beauty products. Only 20% of the respondents purchased electronics and gadgets. This lower percentage is compared to fashion, clothing, and skin care products. Meanwhile, 26.7% of respondents purchase home decor and household items, and 23.3% buy food and beverage items. The data also showed that none of the respondents bought fitness and health products on the platform. Overall, the most popular items purchased on TikTok are fashion, clothing, skincare, and beauty products.

Section 3: Influencer Characteristics

3.1. Characteristics of TikTok Media Influencers that Persuade Consumers to Purchase or Use Promoted Products.

Figure 3.1 Characteristics of TikTok Media Influencers

Respondents were asked what characteristics they prioritized when deciding to purchase a product. Figure 3.1 showed that 76.7% of respondents value the authenticity, positive reputation, and credibility of influencers. According to the study titled “Examining the Effects of Social Media Influencers’ Characteristics on Brand Equity and Purchase Intention” by Es-Safi and Sağlam (2021), authenticity is one of the strengths of influencers. From the perspective of consumers, influencers who promote a product tend to use it themselves and then provide their honest thoughts and ratings. This allows them to gain customers' trust in their credibility by making them believe the reviews are real. Figure 3.1 also showed that two-thirds of respondents (66.7%) consider expertise in the product category to be highly valuable, suggesting that consumers are more likely to buy products promoted by influencers they perceive as experts. Experience plays a crucial role in building a good reputation; as noted by Es-Safi & Sağlam (2021), unskilled influencers may fail to satisfy customers and be dismissed due to their lack of practical knowledge. To effectively influence consumer awareness and purchasing decisions, influencers must enhance their credibility through both knowledge and experience. Additionally, influencers should combine emotional elements with their expertise, as specialized content knowledge can have a significant impact on consumer behavior (Ryu & Han, 2021).

Moreover, it can also be seen from Figure 3.1 that 60% of respondents consider engaging and relatable content to be a key factor in convincing them to make a purchase. Conversely, 40% of respondents believe that a fun and outgoing personality is effective in influencing their buying decisions, highlighting the continued importance of a pleasant demeanor in attracting customers. Physical attractiveness (36.7%) and transparency about sponsorship (33.3%) were valued by

a smaller portion of respondents. While physical appeal might initially draw attention, transparency in sponsorship is critical for maintaining consumer trust.

3.2. The Importance of TikTok Media Influencer Characteristics in Influencing Consumers' Purchasing Decisions

To analyze the importance of influencers' characteristics in influencing consumer purchasing decisions, non-numeric measures were converted into numeric data by assigning numerical values to responses in Likert-type statements: Extremely Important = 5; Important = 4; Neutral = 3; Slightly Important = 2; and Not Important = 1. This data will then be analyzed using descriptive statistics.

3.2.1 Authenticity

Figure 3.2.1. Respondents' Ratings on the Importance of the Authenticity of Influencers in Influencing Their Purchasing Decisions

Figure 3.2.1 showed that most respondents view authenticity as highly important, with 18 respondents rating it as "extremely important" and 9 as "important." This indicates a strong preference for authentic and trustworthy influencers. Only 2 respondents were neutral, and just 1 considered authenticity "not important."

Table 3.2.1. Descriptive Statistics: Importance of Authenticity on Consumers' Purchasing Decisions.

<i>Authenticity</i>	
Mean	4.433333333
Standard Error	0.16388483
Median	5
Mode	5
Standard Deviation	0.897634183
Kurtosis	6.435073247
Skewness	-2.23829552
Range	4
Minimum	1
Maximum	5
Sum	133
Count	30

The mean rating for authenticity is 4.43 (Table 3.2.1), indicating that respondents generally rate it highly. The median and mode are both 5, meaning that half of the respondents and the most common rating consider authenticity "extremely important." The standard deviation of 0.90 shows that most ratings are close to the mean, with a range of 4, suggesting a few lower ratings. The kurtosis of 6.44 indicates a sharp peak and heavier tails, meaning the data is concentrated around the higher ratings. The skewness of -2.23 indicates that higher ratings are much more common than lower ones.

Overall, the data clearly shows that respondents place a high value on authenticity, considering it a crucial factor in their purchasing decisions. This aligns with research by Abreu (2019), which links perceived authenticity with the intention to buy, suggesting that consumers are unlikely to purchase from influencers they perceive as inauthentic.

3.2.2. Physical Attractiveness

Figure 3.2.2 Respondents' Ratings on the Importance of Physical Attractiveness of Influencers in Influencing Their Purchasing Decisions

Figure 3.2.2 shows the distribution of responses on the importance of physical attractiveness. It reveals that most respondents (17) consider it "neutral." However, 10 respondents find it "important." The remaining few are divided into other categories: two find it "not important."

Table 3.2.2 *Descriptive Statistics: Importance of Physical Attractiveness on Consumers' Purchasing Decisions*

Physical Attractiveness	
Mean	3.266666667
Standard Error	0.151113365
Median	3
Mode	3
Standard Deviation	0.827681987
Sample Variance	0.685057471
Kurtosis	2.519658059
Skewness	-0.942344598
Range	4
Minimum	1
Maximum	5
Sum	98
Count	30

As shown in Table 3.2.2, the mean value is 3.27, indicating that the average rating for this characteristic is slightly higher than the midpoint. The median rating is 3, meaning that half of the respondents rated physical attractiveness as 3 or lower. The mode value is also 3, indicating that it is the most frequent rating. The standard deviation of 0.83 suggests a considerable spread around the mean. The kurtosis value of 2.52 is near 3, indicating a mesokurtic distribution, which looks like a normal

distribution but has slightly lighter tails and a flatter peak. The skewness is -0.94, indicating a left-skew. It suggests that there are more ratings above the mean than below it. The mean, median, and mode are all near 3, indicating that respondents had a neutral to slightly positive perception of physical attractiveness. The negative skewness suggests that higher ratings are more prevalent than lower evaluations. The kurtosis value of around 3 indicates a distribution that is similar to a normal distribution but slightly flatter with lighter tails.

Overall, the statistics reveal that while most respondents rate physical attractiveness as either neutral or important, there is a moderate variance in the ratings, with a tendency towards higher values. This indicates that physical attractiveness still affects consumer purchasing decisions. According to Ryu & Han (2021), an attractive celebrity in an advertisement can generate interest in a product or brand and increase consumer identification, leading to more purchases. Additionally, attractiveness plays a significant role in forming interpersonal relationships.

3.2.3. Social Media Status and Presence

Figure 3.2.3. Respondents' Ratings on the Importance of Social Media Status and Presence in Influencing Their Purchasing Decisions

Figure 3.2.3 showed the distribution of responses regarding the importance of

social media presence. Based on Figure 3.2.3, thirteen respondents (43.3%) rated the importance of social media presence as neutral, suggesting it is neither essential nor unimportant. More than half of the respondents see social media presence as important, but to varying degrees: 11 (36.7%) rated it as "important," 4 (13.3%) as "slightly important," and 2 (6.7%) as "extremely important."

Table 3.2.3 *Descriptive Statistics: Importance of Social Media Presence on Consumers' Purchasing Decisions*

Social media presence	
Mean	3.366666667
Standard Error	0.147650826
Median	3
Mode	3
Standard Deviation	0.808716878
Sample Variance	0.654022989
Kurtosis	-0.3430617
Skewness	0.045946761
Range	3
Minimum	2
Maximum	5
Sum	101
Count	30

Table 3.2.3 showed the descriptive analysis of the ratings for the importance of "social media presence." Table 3.2.3 shows that the data has a mean value of 3.37, with "3" being the most common response. The median score is 3, meaning that half of the respondents view social media presence as neutral or slightly important in their purchasing decisions. The kurtosis score of -0.34 indicates a flatter distribution with fewer extreme responses, and the skewness of 0.05 shows a slight right skew, meaning there are a few higher values.

Overall, the findings suggest that respondents view social media presence as neutral to slightly important for their shopping decisions. Therefore, an influencer's social media status has only a minor impact on purchase decisions. However, Janssen et al. (2021) found that consumers generally prefer influencers with larger

followings, as their recommendations tend to have a greater positive effect compared to those from influencers with smaller or moderate followings.

3.2.4. Expertise in the Product Category

Figure 3.2.4 Respondents' Ratings on the Importance of Expertise of Influencers in the Product Category in Influencing Their Purchasing Decisions

Figure 3.2.4 showed the frequency distribution of respondents' views on expertise in the product category. Based on Figure 3.2.4, 10 respondents rated it as "important" and 16 rated it as "extremely important." This indicates a strong preference for competent and informed suggestions or endorsements. A small number of respondents (4) rated its importance as "neutral."

Table 3.2.4. Descriptive Statistics: Importance of Expertise in the Product Category on Consumers' Purchasing Decisions

<i>Expertise in product category</i>	
Mean	4.366666667
Standard Error	0.147650826
Median	5
Mode	5
Standard Deviation	0.808716878
Sample Variance	0.654022989
Kurtosis	1.084975822
Skewness	-1.211380147
Range	3
Minimum	2
Maximum	5
Sum	131
Count	30

Table 3.2.4 showed the descriptive analysis of the ratings for the importance of “expertise in the product category” in terms of influencing the respondents’ purchasing decisions. Based on Table 3.2.4, the data have a mean value of 4.37, with both the median and mode at 5. This reflects a general agreement on the high importance of competence, with most responses leaning towards "important" and "extremely important." The standard deviation of 0.81 shows that responses are consistent and close to the mean. The kurtosis score of -1.21, combined with a left skew, indicates that there are fewer low ratings and that most responses are clustered around higher values. This suggests that most respondents rated competence as highly important. Influencers with expertise in a product category can significantly influence customer awareness and purchasing decisions (Es-Safi & Sağlam, 2021).

3.2.5. Transparency about Sponsorships

Figure 3.2.5 Respondents' Ratings on the Importance of Transparency of Influencers About Sponsorships in Influencing Their Purchasing Decisions

Figure 3.2.5 showed the frequency distribution of respondents' views on the importance of “transparency about sponsorships.” Based on Figure 3.2.5, one-third of the respondents (10) gave neutral ratings. Five respondents rated it as extremely important, while another five rated it as important. On the other hand, four

respondents assessed it as only slightly significant, while the remaining six said it was not important.

Table 3.2.5 *Descriptive Statistics: Importance of Transparency About Sponsorships on Consumers' Purchasing Decisions.*

<i>Transparency about Sponsorships</i>	
Mean	2.966666667
Standard Error	0.246741213
Median	3
Mode	3
Standard Deviation	1.351457281
Sample Variance	1.826436782
Kurtosis	-0.992200209
Skewness	-0.025478539
Range	4
Minimum	1
Maximum	5
Sum	89
Count	30

Based on Table 3.2.5, the ratings for the importance of “transparency about sponsorship” have a mean value of 2.97, indicating a slight neutrality. The median and most frequent rating is 3, reinforcing that neutrality is the most common response. The standard deviation of 1.35 reflects diverse opinions, while the negative kurtosis of -0.99 indicates a more spread-out distribution. The skewness of -0.025 suggests an almost symmetrical distribution, with no strong lean towards positive or negative views.

Overall, respondents are somewhat neutral about transparency in sponsorships. Previous research has shown that sponsorship disclosure can impact consumers' perception of advertisements and their ability to recognize persuasive intent (Lee & Kim, 2020; Ham et al., 2015; Boerman et al., 2014).

3.2.6. Fun and outgoing personality

Figure 3.2.6 *Distribution of Respondent Ratings on the Importance of Fun and Outgoing Personality of Influencers in Influencing Their Purchasing Decisions*

In terms of the influencer’s characteristic of being “fun and having an outgoing personality,” Figure 3.2.6 shows that 11 respondents saw the characteristics as “extremely important,” while another 11 considered them to be “important.”. On the other hand, four respondents rated the importance as only “neutral.” Two respondents regarded it as slightly significant, while another two said it was not important.

Table 3.2.6 *Descriptive Statistics of Rates for the Importance of Fun and Outgoing Personality on Consumers’ Purchasing Decisions*

<i>Fun and outgoing personality</i>	
Mean	3.9
Standard Error	0.216290567
Median	4
Mode	4
Standard Deviation	1.184672223
Sample Variance	1.403448276
Kurtosis	0.673848807
Skewness	-1.127956164
Range	4
Minimum	1
Maximum	5
Sum	117
Count	30

Table 3.2.6 shows the descriptive statistics of respondents' views on the "fun and outgoing personality" trait of influencers. According to Table 3.2.6, the data have an average score of 3.9, indicating a generally positive sentiment. Both the median and mode were 4, further emphasizing that most respondents considered this trait important. Moreover, the results also show that there is a presence of responses towards the lower end of the scale, as evidenced by the negative skewness of -1.13. The kurtosis value of 0.67 suggests that the distribution is more peaked than typical, with the majority of responses grouped around the higher ratings, which implies a perception of both "important" and "extremely important."

In conclusion, despite some variance in responses, the data indicates a general consensus on the importance of a fun and outgoing personality, with many respondents considering it a key factor in their purchasing decisions.

3.2.7. Engaging and Relatable Content

Figure 3.2.7 *Distribution of Respondent Ratings on the Importance of Engaging and Relatable Content of Influencers in Influencing Their Purchasing Decisions*

Figure 3.2.7 shows the frequency distribution of respondents' views on the importance of "engaging and relatable content" in influencing their purchasing

decisions. Based on Figure 3.2.7, the respondents evaluated the "engaging and relatable content" as extremely important (11) and important (10). On the other hand, six respondents rated its relevance as neutral. The remaining three respondents thought it was "slightly important."

Table 3.2.7 *Descriptive Statistics of Rates for the Importance of Engaging and Relatable Content on Consumers' Purchasing Decisions*

<i>Engaging and relatable content</i>	
Mean	3.966666667
Standard Error	0.182469228
Median	4
Mode	5
Standard Deviation	0.999425122
Sample Variance	0.998850575
Kurtosis	-0.673194193
Skewness	-0.59593687
Range	3
Minimum	2
Maximum	5
Sum	119
Count	30

Table 3.2.7 shows the descriptive statistics of respondents' ratings on the importance of "engaging and relatable content." Table 3.2.7 shows that the data have a mean value of 3.97. The mode of 5 and the median value of 4 implied that a significant number of respondents thought that the characteristics of an influencer were a factor in making purchase decisions.

A standard deviation of 0.999 suggests a moderate spread of responses around the mean, with scores ranging from 2 to 5. This indicates that most responses cluster around the "important" and "extremely important" ends of the scale, despite some variation in perceived importance. The left skewness of -0.596 shows a tendency towards higher scores, meaning more respondents viewed engagement and relatable content as important. The kurtosis value of -0.673 indicates a few outliers compared to a normal distribution.

Overall, the data demonstrates that relatable and engaging content significantly influences consumer purchasing decisions. According to Shad et al. (2024), influencers tend to provide content that resonates with their followers. They build a relationship through relatability and engagement, which encourage loyalty and trust. Because of this dynamic, their audience becomes more open to their suggestions and advice, so influencers who are skilled at producing interesting video content are probably going to have a bigger influence on what customers decide to buy.

3.2.8. Positive Reputation and Credibility

Figure 3.2.8 *Distribution of Respondent Ratings on the Importance of Positive Reputation and Credibility of Influencers in Influencing Their Purchasing Decisions*

Figure 3.2.8 shows the frequency distribution of respondents' perceptions of the importance of "positive reputation and credibility" in influencing their purchasing decisions. Based on Figure 3.2.8, the majority of the respondents (19) perceived the characteristics "positive reputation and credibility" as extremely important. On the other hand, seven respondents considered it "important," three gave "neutral" responses, and only one gave a somewhat important rating.

Table 3.2.8 *Descriptive Statistics of Rates for the Importance of Positive Reputation and Credibility on Consumers' Purchasing Decisions*

<i>Positive reputation and credibility</i>	
Mean	4.46666667
Standard Error	0.149584354
Median	5
Mode	5
Standard Deviation	0.819307249
Sample Variance	0.671264368
Kurtosis	1.630632925
Skewness	-1.49821097
Range	3
Minimum	2
Maximum	5
Sum	134
Count	30

Table 3.2.8 shows the descriptive statistics of ratings for the importance of “positive reputation and credibility.” According to Table 3.2.8, the data set has a mean value of 4.47 and a median and mode value of 5. This indicates that most respondents rated these traits as either “important” or “extremely important,” supporting the idea that they have a significant impact on consumers' purchasing decisions. The data also shows a left skewness of -1.50, indicating that many respondents rated credibility and positive reputation at the higher end of the scale. With a kurtosis value of 1.63, the distribution is leptokurtic, meaning it has larger tails and a sharper peak compared to a normal distribution.

Overall, respondents view an influencer's credibility and positive reputation as crucial factors in purchasing decisions. A strong online reputation can help sellers attract customers to their stores (Zahara et al., 2021).

3.3: Characteristics of TikTok Media Influencers that Discourage Consumers from Purchasing a Product

Figure 3.3 Frequency Distribution for the Characteristics of a TikTok Media Influencer that Deters Consumers from Buying or Using a Product

The data provide valuable insights into the respondents' perceptions regarding the characteristics of a TikTok media influencer that discourage them from purchasing or consuming a product. The responses highlight several key factors that negatively impact consumers' buying decisions. Figure 3.3 shows that the two leading characteristics that deter consumers from purchasing or using a product are (1) a lack of transparency (70%) and (2) the negative reputation of the influencer (70%). These results showed how important honesty and reliability are to an influencer's reputation; any impression of these attributes being lacking could sway away potential customers.

The majority of the respondents (63.3%) also cited "lack of authenticity" and "perceived insincerity" as other factors that discourage them from purchasing a product. These show that consumers highly value genuine and sincere endorsements. Factors such as "over-promoting of products" and "poor understanding of the product" were chosen by 50% of the respondents, suggesting that consumers are wary of influencers who promote a product excessively without really having a thorough understanding of the product(s) being promoted. This

emphasizes how important it is that influencers know the products inside and out and strike a balance between advertising and high-quality content. Lastly, 13 respondents, or 43.3%, said that a "lack of transparency" and a "small social media presence" also negatively influence their buying decisions.

3.4: Impact of the Negative Traits of Influencers on Consumers' Decisions Not to Buy a Product

To analyze the impact of influencers' negative characteristics on consumers' purchasing decisions, non-numeric measures were converted into numeric data by assigning numerical values as follows: high impact = 4; significant impact = 3; minimal impact = 2; and no impact = 1. The data were then analyzed using descriptive statistics.

3.4.1. Influencer's Lack of Authenticity

Figure 3.4.1 *Distribution of Respondent Ratings on the Impact of Influencer's Lack of Authenticity on Their Purchasing Decisions*

The data analyzes how a lack of authenticity among influencers affects purchasing decisions. According to Figure 3.4.1, 18 respondents felt the lack of authenticity had a "high impact" on their decisions, while 11 found it significant but not high. Only 1 respondent considered the impact "minimal."

Table 3.4.1 *Descriptive Statistics: Impact of Influencer’s Lack of Authenticity on Consumers’ Purchasing Decisions.*

<i>Lack of Authenticity</i>	
Mean	3.566666667
Standard Error	0.103760703
Median	4
Mode	4
Standard Deviation	0.568320777
Sample Variance	0.322988506
Kurtosis	-0.168419491
Skewness	-0.882021195
Range	2
Minimum	2
Maximum	4
Sum	107
Count	30

Table 3.4.1 shows the descriptive statistics of ratings for the impact of “lack of authenticity.” among TikTok influencers on consumers’ purchasing decisions. According to Table 3.4.1, the data has a mean value of 3.57 and a median and mode values of 4, which indicates that a substantial number of respondents believe that the lack of authenticity significantly impacts their decision-making. The standard deviation of 0.57 shows that responses are fairly consistent and mainly skew towards higher ratings. The left skewness of -0.88 reflects a tendency towards higher impact ratings, suggesting more respondents see the lack of authenticity as having a significant negative effect. The kurtosis score of -0.17 indicates a distribution close to normal, with a slightly flatter peak and fewer extreme values.

Overall, the analysis suggests that a lack of authenticity among TikTok influencers is seen as a major negative factor in consumer purchasing decisions. In the study conducted by Mishra and Ashfaq (2023), they found out that the authenticity and trustworthiness of the influencers are highly significant towards consumer opinions and purchasing intentions, thus directly affecting consumers' purchasing decisions.

3.4.2. Respondents' Perceived Influencer's Insincerity

Figure 3.4.2 Respondents' Ratings of the Impact of Influencer's Perceived Insincerity on Their Purchasing Decisions.

Figure 3.4.2 shows the frequency distribution of respondents' perceptions of the impact of "perceived insincerity" on their purchasing decisions. Based on Figure 3.4.2, more than 50% (17) of the respondents viewed the "perceived insincerity" as having a significant impact on their purchasing decisions. While 11 respondents agreed that it has a high impact, two (2) respondents deemed such characteristics to only have a minimal impact.

Table 3.4.2 Descriptive Statistics of Rates for the Impact of Influencers' Perceived Insincerity on Consumers' Purchasing Decisions

<i>Perceived insincerity</i>	
Mean	3.3
Standard Error	0.108807539
Median	3
Mode	3
Standard Deviation	0.595963433
Sample Variance	0.355172414
Kurtosis	-0.482055517
Skewness	-0.188508154
Range	2
Minimum	2
Maximum	4
Sum	99
Count	30

Table 3.4.2 shows the descriptive statistics of ratings for the impact of

“perceived insincerity” among influencers on consumers’ purchasing decisions. Based on Table 3.4.2, the data has a mean score of 3.3, which indicates that respondents see perceived insincerity as having a moderate impact on their decision-making. The median and mode values of 3 suggest that some respondents view insincerity as either minimally or significantly impactful, implying a range of perceptions. The standard deviation of 0.60 shows moderate variability in responses, with evaluations mainly clustering around the middle of the scale. The slight left skewness of -0.19 indicates a minor tendency towards higher ratings, suggesting that more respondents view insincerity as having a significant impact. The kurtosis score of -0.48 indicates a distribution slightly flatter than normal, with few outliers. The analysis suggests that perceived insincerity among TikTok influencers has a notable effect on customer purchasing decisions. Chan & Sengupta (2010) found in their study titled "Insincere Flattery Actually Works: A Dual Attitudes Perspective" that even insincere compliments can influence consumers' automatic reactions, making such flattery persuasive in shaping initial responses to marketers.

3.4.3. Influencer’s Small Social Media Presence

Figure 3.4.3 Respondents' Ratings on the Impact of Influencer’s Small Social Media Presence on Their Purchasing Decisions

Figure 3.4.3 showed the frequency distribution of responses regarding the impact of the “small social media presence” of influencers on consumers’ purchasing decisions. According to Figure 3.4.3, twelve respondents (40%) felt a "small social media presence" had minimal impact on their buying decisions. However, 7 respondents saw it as having a high impact, and 9 saw it as significant. Only 2 respondents felt it had no impact. The mean score of 2.7 suggests that respondents generally view a small social media presence as minimally impactful.

Table 3.4.3 *Descriptive Statistics: Impact of the Small Social Media Presence of Influencers on Consumers’ Purchasing Decisions*

<i>Small social media presence</i>	
Mean	2.7
Standard Error	0.167126
Median	3
Mode	2
Standard Deviation	0.915386
Sample Variance	0.837931
Kurtosis	-0.94178
Skewness	0.080921
Range	3
Minimum	1
Maximum	4
Sum	81
Count	30

Table 3.4.3 showed the descriptive statistics of the data for the ratings of the impact of “small social media presence” on consumers’ purchasing decisions. Based on Table 3.4.3, the data set has a mean value of 2.7, a median value of 3, and a mode of 2. This showed that while many see social media presence as slightly impactful, others believe it is somewhat significant. The standard deviation of 0.92 indicates moderate variation in responses. A skewness of 0.08 shows a nearly symmetrical distribution, and the kurtosis value of -0.94 suggests a flatter distribution with fewer extreme values. Overall, most respondents view the impact of a small social media presence as moderate.

3.4.4. Influencers' Over Promotion of Products

Figure 3.4.4 Respondents' Ratings on the Impact of Over Promoting Products on Their Purchasing Decisions

The findings revealed how over-promoting products affects consumer purchasing decisions. Figure 3.4.4, showed that 11 respondents felt it had a high impact, and 10 thought it had a significant impact. In contrast, 7 respondents saw it as having only a minor impact, and 2 saw it as having no impact.

Table 3.4.4 Descriptive Statistics: Impact of Over Promoting Products on Consumers' Purchasing Decisions

<i>Overpromoting products</i>	
Mean	3
Standard Error	0.172873
Median	3
Mode	4
Standard Deviation	0.946864
Sample Variance	0.896552
Kurtosis	-0.69865
Skewness	-0.52226
Range	3
Minimum	1
Maximum	4
Sum	90
Count	30

Table 3.4.4 showed the descriptive statistics of ratings for the impact of “over promoting products” on consumers' purchasing decisions. Based on Table 3.4.4, the data set has a mean and median value of both 3, indicating that most responses are

around the midpoint of the impact scale. The mode is 4, suggesting that "high impact" is the most common view. The standard deviation of 0.95 shows a range of opinions, with some seeing over-promotion as minor and others as significant or high. The skewness of -0.52 indicates a slight tendency toward higher ratings, meaning most respondents view over-promotion negatively, though a few are less affected. The kurtosis value of -0.698 shows a relatively flat distribution with few outliers.

In summary, while there are some variations in opinions, most respondents believe that over-promoting products generally has a high impact on purchasing decisions. This suggests that influencers' over-promotion typically affects consumers' decisions significantly. Excessive promotion can have a saturating effect on customers, leading to promotional messages becoming conventional and losing their appeal. Promotions that are excessively frequent may also undermine consumer trust, eventually affecting consumers' purchasing decisions (Aripin & Pynatih, 2023).

3.4.5. Influencer's Poor Understanding of the Product.

Figure 3.4.5 Respondents Ratings on the Impact of Influencer's Poor Understanding of the Product on Their Purchasing Decisions

The data provides insights into respondents' assessments of the impact of influencers' poor product knowledge on consumer purchasing decisions. According to Figure 3.4.5, 22 respondents believe a poor understanding of the product has a high impact on their purchasing decisions, while 7 see it as having a significant impact.

Table 3.4.5 *Descriptive Statistics: Impact of Poor Understanding of the Product on Consumers' Purchasing Decisions*

<i>Poor understanding of the product</i>	
Mean	3.7
Standard Error	0.0976741
Median	4
Mode	4
Standard Deviation	0.5349831
Sample Variance	0.2862069
Kurtosis	1.9504524
Skewness	-1.6214903
Range	2
Minimum	2
Maximum	4
Sum	111
Count	30

Table 3.4.5 showed the descriptive statistics of ratings for the impact of influencers' "poor understanding of the product" on consumers' purchasing decisions. Based on Table 3.4.5, the data set has a mean value of 3.7, with a median and mode values of 4. This indicates that most responses are clustered around the "significant" to "high-impact" end. The standard deviation of 0.53 reflects some variation around the mean, with responses generally favoring higher ratings. The skewness value of -1.62 shows a left skew, meaning higher ratings are more common. The kurtosis value of 1.95 suggests a leptokurtic distribution with a sharper peak and fatter tails, indicating responses are more concentrated around the mean with a few outliers. Overall, most respondents view a poor understanding of the product as having a significant to high impact on their purchasing decisions.

Khan et al. (2023) study showed that influencers' content and product knowledge distribution skills significantly impact a company's sales and brand image. Influencers tend to build their influence by providing product knowledge to others. Therefore, by effectively delivering product knowledge, they enhance their influence over consumers. In summary, this could imply that consumers tend to place high importance on influencers being knowledgeable and well-informed about the things they endorse; hence, the lack of understanding of the product deters them from purchasing it.

3.4.6 Influencer's Lack of Transparency

Figure 3.4.6 Respondents' Ratings on the Impact of Influencers' Lack of Transparency on Their Purchasing Decisions

The data gathered showed a significant trend in respondents' perceptions of the impact of influencers' lack of transparency on purchasing decisions. According to Figure 3.4.6, more than 50% (16) of the respondents said that the lack of transparency had a high impact on their purchasing decisions. Twelve (12) respondents thought it had a significant impact, while the other two thought it had a minimal impact. On the other hand, no respondents chose no impact. With a mean score of 3.47 (out of 4), it is clear that a lack of transparency is often seen as having a significant effect. While most respondents view the lack of transparency as having

a significant to high impact, a small minority sees it as having minimal impact.

Table 3.4.6 *Descriptive Statistics: Impact of Influencers' Lack of Transparency on Consumers' Purchasing Decisions*

<i>Lack of Transparency</i>	
Mean	3.46666667
Standard Error	0.11480451
Median	4
Mode	4
Standard Deviation	0.62881022
Sample Variance	0.3954023
Kurtosis	-0.3206849
Skewness	-0.7581686
Range	2
Minimum	2
Maximum	4
Sum	104
Count	30

Table 3.4.6 showed the descriptive statistics of ratings for the impact of “lack of transparency” on consumers’ purchasing decisions. According to Table 3.4.6, the data set has a mean of 3.46 and a median and mode values of 4, indicating that the most common response has a high impact. The sample variance of 0.40 shows some variation in responses, but the low kurtosis of -0.32 and skewness of -0.76 suggest that responses are generally clustered around higher impact values, with more high-impact than low-impact responses. Overall, the data indicates that transparency is highly valued, with most consumers agreeing that its absence significantly influences their purchasing decisions. Woodroof et al. (2020) found that transparency fosters positive relationships between customers and businesses. Thus, when consumers see TikTok media influencers' postings with clear disclosures, their perceptions of influencer transparency and product efficacy improve, resulting in increased purchasing intentions.

3.4.7 Influencer’s Negative Reputation

Figure 3.4.7 Respondent's Ratings on the Impact of Influencers’ Negative Reputation on Their Purchasing Decisions

Figure 3.4.7 showed the frequency distribution of ratings for the impact of “negative reputation” on consumers’ purchasing decisions. The data gathered presented a persuasive picture of consumer attitudes toward the impact of an influencer's negative reputation on purchasing decisions. Based on Figure 3.4.7, twenty-one (70%) of the respondents considered a negative reputation to have a “high impact” on their purchasing decisions, while five agreed that it had a significant impact. Only three people believed it had a “minimal impact,” and one thought it had “no impact” at all.

Table 3.4.7 Descriptive Statistics: Impact of Negative Reputation on Consumers’ Purchasing Decisions

<i>Negative Reputation</i>	
Mean	3.5333333
Standard Error	0.1495844
Median	4
Mode	4
Standard Deviation	0.8193072
Sample Variance	0.6712644
Kurtosis	2.2331314
Skewness	-1.7263164
Range	3
Minimum	1
Maximum	4
Sum	106
Count	30

Table 3.4.7 showed the descriptive statistics of ratings for the impact of influencers' "negative reputation" on consumers' purchasing decisions. According to Table 3.4.7, the data has a mean score of 3.53 and both median and mode scores of 4. Respondents clearly believe that a negative influencer's reputation significantly impacts their purchasing decisions. The negative skewness of -1.73 and high kurtosis of 2.23 indicate that responses are heavily concentrated at the high-impact end, with fewer responses at the lower end and a sharper peak with more extreme values. In conclusion, maintaining a positive reputation is crucial for influencers, as a negative reputation can undermine consumer trust and reduce their influence on purchasing behavior. Based on the study conducted by Jung & Seock (2016) titled "The Impact of Corporate Reputation on Brand Attitude and Purchase Intention," it appears that a negative reputation tends to worsen consumers' brand attitude and purchase intention.

Section 4: Influencers' Techniques

4.1. Techniques Used by TikTok Media Influencers in Persuading Consumers to Purchase a Product

Figure 4.1 *Techniques Used by TikTok Media Influencers in Persuading Consumers*

Respondents were asked about the marketing techniques used by TikTok influencers that persuade them to purchase products. The top techniques chosen

(Figure 4.1) by the respondents are demonstrating the product's use and providing honest reviews, each cited by 28 respondents (93.3%). This suggests consumers highly value seeing products in action and trust genuine feedback. Interactive content, such as Q&A sessions and polls, and limited-time offers or discounts, are also effective, as cited by 27 respondents (90%). These techniques engage the audience and create urgency. Collaborations with other influencers were mentioned by 12 respondents (40%), while behind-the-scenes content was the least effective, with only 10 respondents (33.3%) finding it persuasive.

4.2. The Effectiveness of the Influencer's Techniques in Persuading Consumers to Purchase a Product

To analyze the effectiveness of influencers' techniques on consumers' purchasing decisions, non-numeric measures were converted into numeric data by assigning numerical values as follows: Very Effective = 4, Effective = 3, Slightly Effective = 2, and Not Effective = 1. This data was then analyzed using descriptive statistics.

4.2.1. Demonstrating Product Use

Figure 4.2.1 Respondents' Ratings on the Effectiveness of Demonstrating Product Use on Their Purchasing Decisions

The data highlights the effectiveness of demonstrating product use as a persuasive technique. Figure 4.2.1 shows the frequency distribution of ratings regarding the effectiveness of “demonstrating product use” on persuading consumers. According to Figure 4.2.1, 21 respondents (70%) rated this technique as "very effective," while 8 respondents (26.7%) considered it "effective." Only 1 respondent (3.3%) rated it as "slightly effective." Overall, most participants agreed that this technique significantly influences their purchasing decisions.

Table 4.2.1 *Descriptive Statistics: Effectiveness of Demonstrating Product Use on Persuading Consumers*

<i>Demonstrating Product Use</i>	
Mean	3.666667
Standard Error	0.099808
Median	4
Mode	4
Standard Deviation	0.546672
Sample Variance	0.298851
Kurtosis	1.201183
Skewness	-1.40712
Range	2
Minimum	2
Maximum	4
Sum	110
Count	30

Table 4.2.1 showed the descriptive statistics of ratings on the effectiveness of “demonstrating product use.” According to Table 4.2.1, the mean is 3.67, with both the median and mode at 4, indicating a high perceived effectiveness. The standard deviation is 0.55, showing general agreement among respondents. The negative skewness of -1.41 suggests most responses are clustered at the higher end of the effectiveness scale. Additionally, the kurtosis value of 1.20 indicates a distribution with a sharper peak, centered around the "Very Effective" rating. Product demonstrations, according to Heiman and Muller (1996), allow the consumer to try the product or service before making a purchase decision. The demonstration

familiarizes the public with the product's features and reduces client resistance to sales efforts.

4.2.2. Providing an Honest Review

Figure 4.2.2 Respondents' Ratings on the Effectiveness of Providing an Honest Review on Persuading Consumers

Seventeen respondents (56.7%) rated providing honest reviews as "very effective," 12 respondents (40%) as "effective," and one respondent (3.3%) as "slightly effective" (Figure 4.2.2).

Table 4.2.2 Descriptive Statistics: Effectiveness of Providing an Honest Review on Persuading Consumers

<i>Providing Honest Review</i>	
Mean	3.53333333
Standard Error	0.10431312
Median	4
Mode	4
Standard Deviation	0.57134646
Sample Variance	0.32643678
Kurtosis	-0.4294074
Skewness	-0.7324996
Range	2
Minimum	2
Maximum	4
Sum	106
Count	30

The data showed a mean value of 3.53 and a median and mode values of 4, indicating high perceived effectiveness. The standard deviation of 0.57 shows some

variability in responses. The kurtosis value of -0.43 suggests a flatter distribution with moderate variation, while the skewness of -0.73 indicates a slight lean towards higher ratings, showing a concentration of responses at the higher end of the scale (Table 4.2.2).

Overall, the data suggest that providing honest reviews is highly effective in persuading consumers. Consumers rely heavily on online product reviews from influencers and others to make purchasing decisions (Ansari & Gupta, 2021). An honest product review has a greater positive impact on trust than a fraudulent one (de Bont, 2022). Therefore, the increased perceived credibility of influencers enhances their ability to persuade consumers.

4.2.3. Engaging Storytelling

Figure 4.2.3 Respondents' Ratings on the Effectiveness of Engaging Storytelling on Persuading Consumers

Junior et al. (2023) found that storytelling significantly influences consumer emotions and purchasing decisions. In this study, Figure 4.2.3 showed that 14 respondents (46.7%) rated storytelling as "effective," 10 (33.3%) as "slightly effective," 5 (16.7%) as "very effective," and 1 (3.3%) as "not effective."

Table 4.2.3 *Descriptive Statistics: Effectiveness of Engaging Storytelling on Persuading Consumers*

<i>Engaging Storytelling</i>	
Mean	2.766666667
Standard Error	0.14128583
Median	3
Mode	3
Standard Deviation	0.773854363
Sample Variance	0.598850575
Kurtosis	-0.40308154
Skewness	-0.03685007
Range	3
Minimum	1
Maximum	4
Sum	83
Count	30

Table 4.2.3 showed the descriptive statistics of ratings for the effectiveness of “engaging storytelling” in persuading consumers to make a purchase. The data has a mean score of 2.77, with median and mode values of 3. This shows that respondents generally view storytelling as "effective." The standard deviation of 0.77 indicates some variability in responses. The kurtosis of -0.40 suggests a slightly flatter distribution, while the skewness of -0.04 indicates a nearly symmetrical distribution. Overall, while storytelling has a notable impact on purchasing decisions, opinions on its effectiveness vary among respondents.

4.2.4 Interactive Content

Figure 4.2.4 *Respondents' Ratings on the Effectiveness of Interactive Content on Persuading Consumers.*

The data on the impact of TikTok media influencers' interactive content provides valuable insights on how this technique influences consumer purchasing decisions. Figure 4.2.4 showed that 16 respondents (53.3%) rated interactive content as "effective," 7 (23.3%) as "slightly effective," 5 (16.7%) as "very effective," and only 2 (6.7%) rated it as "not effective."

Table 4.2.4 *Descriptive Statistics: Effectiveness of Interactive Content on Persuading Consumers*

<i>Interactive Content</i>	
Mean	2.8
Standard Error	0.14700066
Median	3
Mode	3
Standard Deviation	0.8051558
Sample Variance	0.64827586
Kurtosis	0.12034103
Skewness	-0.4586701
Range	3
Minimum	1
Maximum	4
Sum	84
Count	30

The data gathered have a mean score of 2.8, suggesting a moderate level of effectiveness for interactive content, with a median and mode of 3 indicating that "effective" is the most common perception (Table 4.2.4) . The standard deviation of 0.81 reflects a wide range of opinions. The kurtosis of 0.12 and negative skew of -0.46 point to a slightly peaked distribution with a notable spread in responses.

In summary, interactive content is generally seen as effective, though its impact varies significantly among individuals. Its nature encourages active participation, which can boost engagement rates. In a study by Pal (2023), it was found that involving the audience in the content creation process enables influencers to form stronger bonds with their followers, which can provide a more positive outcome for consumers' purchasing decisions.

4.2.5. Limited-time offers or Discounts

Figure 4.2.5 *Distribution of Respondent Ratings on the Effectiveness of Limited-Time Offers or Discounts on Persuading Consumers*

Figure 4.2.5 shows the frequency distribution of responses regarding the effectiveness of “limited-time offers or discounts” on persuading consumers. According to Figure 4.2.5, five respondents (16.7%) found limited-time offers or discounts “very effective,” 46.7% considered them “effective,” and 33.3% deemed them “slightly effective.” Only one respondent (3.3%) found this tactic “not effective.”

Table 4.2.5 *Descriptive Statistics of Rates for the Effectiveness of Limited-Time Offers or Discounts on Persuading Consumers*

<i>Limited Time Offers or Discounts</i>	
Mean	3.13333333
Standard Error	0.13333333
Median	3
Mode	3
Standard Deviation	0.73029674
Sample Variance	0.53333333
Kurtosis	-1.0190887
Skewness	-0.2141649
Range	2
Minimum	2
Maximum	4
Sum	94
Count	30

Table 4.2.5 showed that the ratings for “limited-time offers or discounts” have a mean score of 3.13, with both the median and mode at 3. This implies that most respondents view this technique as “effective” for influencing purchasing decisions.

The standard deviation of 0.73 shows some variability in opinions. The slight negative skewness (-0.21) indicates a tendency toward more effective ratings, while the platykurtic kurtosis value of -1.01 suggests a flatter distribution with fewer extreme values.

Overall, limited-time offers and discounts are generally seen as effective persuasion techniques. According to Lin et al. (2015), dynamic discount strategies are employed by marketers to convey scarcity messages, which increase consumers' purchase intentions. The stronger the purchase intention, the higher the likelihood of making a purchase.

4.2.6. Collaborations with Other Influencers

Figure 4.2.6 *Distribution of Respondent Ratings on the Effectiveness of Collaboration with Other Influencers on Persuading Consumers.*

Figure 4.2.6 showed the frequency distribution of responses regarding the effectiveness of “collaboration with other influencers.” in persuading consumers. Based on Figure 4.2.6, it revealed that 40% (12 respondents) rated collaboration with other influencers as "slightly effective," 23.3% rated it "very effective," and 26.7% found it "effective." Only 10% (3 respondents) considered it "not effective."

Table 4.2.6 *Descriptive Statistics of Rates for the Effectiveness of Collaboration with Other Influencers on Persuading Consumers.*

<i>Collaboration</i>	
Mean	2.633333333
Standard Error	0.176057288
Median	2.5
Mode	2
Standard Deviation	0.964305479
Sample Variance	0.929885057
Kurtosis	-0.990073487
Skewness	0.088264455
Range	3
Minimum	1
Maximum	4
Sum	79
Count	30

Table 4.2.6 showed the descriptive statistics of ratings regarding the effectiveness of "collaboration with other influencers." Based on Table 4.2.6, the mean score of 2.63 suggests that respondents generally view this technique as between "Slightly Effective" and "Effective." The median of 2.5 indicates a slight tilt toward "Slightly Effective," and the mode is 2, the most common rating. The standard deviation of 0.96 shows variability in responses, with most opinions clustered around average effectiveness. The kurtosis value of -0.99 indicates a platykurtic distribution, meaning the distribution is flatter with fewer outliers than normal. The skewness of 0.088 shows a slight positive skew, suggesting lower ratings and a longer tail on the right side of the distribution.

Overall, respondents generally see collaboration with other influencers as moderately or slightly effective, though opinions vary, with some seeing it as highly effective and others as not effective at all. The information, videos, and stories that influencers share help them create close connections with their audience and impact their purchasing decisions (Mussa, 2023). Thus, brands and other influencers have viewed the collaboration as an opportunity that they can use to tailor their content to a large audience through those influencers' pages (Fleming, 2020).

4.2.7. Behind-the-scenes content

Figure 4.2.7 Frequency Distribution of Respondent Ratings on the Effectiveness of Providing an Honest Review on Persuading Consumers.

Customers are becoming more interested in the stories behind the products and services they use. When customers see the behind-the-scenes activities of a small firm, it helps to humanize the brand. Moreover, behind-the-scenes content can reach consumers who are not generally part of the target market, impact them, and direct them to the company's website, which eventually enables more purchases with little effort (Bergh, 2024). In this study, Figure 4.2.7 shows that 12 respondents (40%) rated the technique as "slightly effective," 8 (26.7%) as "effective," 5 (16.7%) as "very effective," and 5 (16.7%) as "not effective."

Table 4.2.7 Descriptive Statistics of Rates for the Effectiveness of Behind-the-Scenes Content on Persuading Consumers.

<i>Behind the scenes content</i>	
Mean	2.433333333
Standard Error	0.177358221
Median	2
Mode	2
Standard Deviation	0.971430986
Sample Variance	0.943678161
Kurtosis	-0.83780194
Skewness	0.200794801
Range	3
Minimum	1
Maximum	4
Sum	73
Count	30

Table 4.2.7 showed that the data set for the ratings of effectiveness of “behind-the-scene content” has a mean score of 2.43, which suggests an average rating skewed toward “slightly effective.” The median and mode of 2 confirm this as the most common rating. A standard deviation of 0.97 indicates moderate variability in responses. Most ratings cluster in the middle of the scale, with a slight positive skew of 0.20 suggesting a tendency toward higher effectiveness ratings. The kurtosis of -0.84 shows a flatter distribution with fewer extreme values than normal. Overall, the data indicates that behind-the-scenes content has only moderate success in influencing consumers' purchasing decisions.

4.3. Ineffective Techniques Used by TikTok Influencers in Persuading Consumers

Figure 4.3 *Ineffective Techniques Used for Persuading Consumers*

Twenty-three respondents (76.7%) find overly scripted content ineffective, 20 respondents (66.7%) see excessive product promotion as ineffective, while 16 (53.3%) view generic content as ineffective, favoring unique and creative approaches. Additionally, 15 respondents (50%) consider hidden sponsorship ineffective, indicating a preference for transparency (Figure 4.3).

4.4. Impact of techniques that are perceived as ineffective

To analyze the ineffective techniques used by influencers' on consumers' purchasing decisions, non-numeric measures were converted into numeric data by assigning numerical values as follows: high impact (4), significant impact (3), minimal impact (2), and no impact (1). These data were then analyzed using descriptive statistics.

4.4.1. Excessive Promotion

Figure 4.4.1 Respondents' Ratings on the Impact of Excessive Promotion on Consumers' Purchasing Decisions

Figure 4.4.1 showed the frequency distribution of ratings regarding the impact of “excessive promotion.” Sixteen respondents (53.33%) viewed excessive promotion as having a high impact on their purchasing decisions, while nine respondents (30%) considered it to have a significant impact. In contrast, 4 respondents (13.33%) rated its impact as minimal, and 1 respondent (3.33%) saw it as having no impact.

Table 4.4.1 Descriptive Statistics: The Impact of Excessive Promotion on Consumers' Purchasing Decisions

<i>Excessive Promotion</i>	
Mean	3.333333333
Standard Error	0.154125888
Median	4
Mode	4
Standard Deviation	0.844182254
Sample Variance	0.712643678
Kurtosis	0.467741935
Skewness	-1.091777257
Range	3
Minimum	1
Maximum	4
Sum	100
Count	30

Table 4.4.1 showed that the average rating for the impact of excessive promotion is 3.33 (mean), suggesting that the majority of respondents believe the impact is between "significant impact" and "high impact." The median number is 4, suggesting that half of the respondents rated "high impact" while half were other measures on the scale. The mode was 4, indicating that "high impact" was the most prevalent perception among respondents. The standard deviation is 0.84, suggesting that the majority of the distribution is averagely spread out from the mean; there is some diversity in the evaluations provided by respondents. The kurtosis is positive (0.47), indicating a leptokurtic distribution with heavier tails than normal; more data are clustered around the mean. The negative skew of -1.09 suggests that many respondents leaned toward the high rating about the impact of excessive promotion.

Overall, the findings suggest that despite the diversity in responses, the majority agrees that excessive promotion impacts their purchasing decisions. Excessive promotion reduces the appeal of the product being endorsed, which in turn reduces the purchasing intention of the consumers.

4.2. Generic or Unoriginal Content

Figure 4.4.2 *Respondents' Ratings on the Impact of Generic or Unoriginal Content on Consumers' Purchasing Decisions*

Figure 4.4.2 showed the frequency distribution of responses regarding the impact of “generic or unoriginal content” on consumers’ purchasing decisions. Thirteen respondents (43.33%) said that generic and unoriginal content highly impacted their decision-making in terms of product purchasing. Another 13 respondents (43.33%) believed that such an approach had a significant impact. This suggests that unoriginal information had a significant and unfavorable impact on a large section of the audience. Four respondents (13.33%) said that generic and unoriginal content had minimal impact. This means that a small percentage of the audience is somewhat indifferent or only slightly affected by the lack of originality in the content.

Table 4.4.2 *Descriptive Statistics: The Impact of Generic or Unoriginal Content on Consumers’ Purchasing Decisions.*

<i>Generic or unoriginal content</i>	
Mean	3.3
Standard Error	0.12821
Median	3
Mode	3
Standard Deviation	0.70221
Sample Variance	0.4931
Kurtosis	-0.78134
Skewness	-0.49935
Range	2
Minimum	2
Maximum	4
Sum	99
Count	30

The mean rating for the responses regarding generic and unoriginal content is 3.3, suggesting that respondents generally view its impact as between "significant" and "high" (Table 4.4.2) The median and mode are both 3, indicating that "significant impact" is the most common perception. The standard deviation of 0.70 reflects moderate variation in responses. The negative skewness of -0.50 indicates a slight left skew, with most ratings leaning towards "high" or "significant" impact.

The data indicate that general and unoriginal techniques significantly impact consumers' purchasing decisions, suggesting that such a technique mostly deters consumers from making a purchase. According to Mazerant et al. (2021), creativity is crucial for effective advertising. This creativity positively influences attention, recall, attitudes toward the brand, online sharing behavior, and purchase intentions. Therefore, creating meaningful and relevant content can significantly enhance its value and importance to consumers. Additionally, previous research by Farace et al. (2017) demonstrated that visual attractiveness and aesthetic quality are key factors in eliciting a positive consumer response.

4.4.3. Hidden Sponsorships

Figure 4.4.3 Respondents' Ratings on the Impact of Hidden Sponsorships on Consumers' Purchasing Decisions.

As shown in Figure 4.4.3, twelve respondents (40%) rated content with hidden sponsorships as "highly impactful." Approximately one-third of the respondents (10, or 33.33%) considered it to be "significantly impactful." Six respondents (20%) reported that such content had a "minimal impact," while only two respondents (6.67%) felt it had "no impact" at all. This indicates that a small percentage of the audience perceives the impact as less than moderate.

Table 4.4.3 *Descriptive Statistics: The Impact of Hidden Sponsorships on Consumers' Purchasing Decisions*

<i>Hidden Sponsorships</i>	
Mean	3.066666667
Standard Error	0.172429118
Median	3
Mode	4
Standard Deviation	0.944433176
Sample Variance	0.891954023
Kurtosis	-0.492319284
Skewness	-0.665866041
Range	3
Minimum	1
Maximum	4
Sum	92
Count	30

The mean rating for the responses regarding the impact of "hidden sponsorship" is 3.07 (Table 4.4.3), suggesting that, on average, respondents view the impact as slightly greater than "significant impact." The median rating is 3, indicating that half of the respondents considered the impact to be "significant." The mode is 4, indicating that "high impact" is the most common perception among respondents.

The standard deviation is 0.94, reflecting a reasonable degree of variation from the mean. The platykurtic kurtosis score of -0.492 suggests that the data distribution is flatter and less peaked than a normal distribution. The negative

skewness value of -0.666 indicates that the distribution is left-skewed, meaning that more respondents rated the impact as high, while fewer rated it as minimal or having no impact. The statistics demonstrate that most respondents believe hidden sponsorships have a significant impact on their perception and decision-making, which also implies the importance of transparency and authenticity in sponsorships for fostering favorable consumer perception and trust.

4.4.4. Overly Scripted Content

Figure 4.4.4 Respondents' Ratings on the Impact of Overly Scripted Content on Consumers' Purchasing Decisions.

With regard to the impact of overly scripted content on consumers' purchasing decisions, Figure 4.4.4 showed that 5 respondents (16.67%) felt that overly scripted content had minimal impact. In contrast, 9 respondents (30%) believed that overly scripted content had a significant impact, suggesting that a notable portion of the audience found it to be quite influential. While more than half of the respondents, 16 (53.33%), believed that overly scripted content had a high impact, these findings show that, while there is some variation in responses, the overall trend is that overly scripted content is perceived as highly impactful.

Table 4.4.4 *Descriptive Statistics: The Impact of Overly Scripted Content on Consumers' Purchasing Decisions.*

<i>Overly Scripted Content</i>	
Mean	3.366666667
Standard Error	0.13964926
Median	4
Mode	4
Standard Deviation	0.764890496
Sample Variance	0.585057471
Kurtosis	-0.83646758
Skewness	-0.75477795
Range	2
Minimum	2
Maximum	4
Sum	101
Count	30

As shown in Table 4.4.4, the average impact rating of “overly scripted content” is 3.37, between 'Significant Impact' and 'High Impact.’ This indicates that respondents frequently rate the impact in this range. The median and mode scores are both 4, suggesting that half of the respondents and the most common rating view the impact as 'High Impact.' The standard deviation of 0.76 indicates moderate variation in responses. A kurtosis value of -0.836 suggests the data is more spread out and less peaked than a normal distribution, with lighter tails. The skewness of -0.755 shows a left-skewed distribution, meaning more respondents rated the impact as high, while fewer rated it as low.

In their study, Cocker et al. (2021) identified common issues in social media influencer marketing, highlighting that overly scripted or staged endorsements are major problems. These types of endorsements can reduce the audience's enjoyment of the content. Endorsements that appear fake or too prepared might undermine the audience's enjoyment of and trust in the influencer. Therefore, this type of content may appear inauthentic, making followers less likely to interact with or trust the promoted products or services.

Section 5: Consumer Experience

This section explores consumers' experiences with online product purchases, including the key factors that influence their decisions, their typical reactions when a product fails to meet expectations, and tips on how to avoid falling victim to deceptive marketing tactics by TikTok media influencers.

5.1. Other Factors that Convinced Consumers to Make a Purchase

Figure 5.1 . Additional Factors Influencing Respondents' Purchasing Decisions

Respondents were asked about other factors that influence their purchasing decisions. The majority indicated that price and necessity are the main factors (Table 5.1), with 9 respondents (30%) citing price and 8 respondents (26%) citing necessity. Curiosity also plays a role, with 5 respondents (16%) purchasing products out of curiosity. External influences, such as positive reviews and recommendations, significantly impact buying decisions, as respondents mentioned that trust in others' opinions affects their own trust in a product. Product qualities like usability, design, and authenticity also influence about one-third of consumer decisions. Special deals, like limited-time discounts, are important factors as well. Additionally, exposure to products through algorithms can affect buyers' choices.

5.2. Consumer Reactions When Influencer-Promoted Products Don't Meet Expectations.

Figure 5.2 Actions Taken by Consumers for Unsatisfactory Purchases

Figure 5.2 showed how consumers reacted when a product recommended by an influencer did not meet their expectations. Each respondent provided multiple recommendations or actions to take. Most respondents (70%) indicated they would leave a negative review or rating. This suggests that dissatisfied consumers are likely to voice their discontent publicly, potentially damaging the reputations of both the influencer and the product. Additionally, 36.7% of respondents said they would request a refund, indicating that many customers actively seek their money back when a product does not meet their expectations.

Furthermore, 23.3% of participants mentioned they would comment directly on the influencer's post, hoping to resolve the issue or warn other potential buyers. Similarly, 16.7% said they would leave a comment on the TikTok post, showing that specific social media platforms are used to voice complaints. However, 23.3% of participants indicated they would take no action, suggesting that some consumers either don't feel strongly enough to respond or prefer to avoid conflict. The least common actions were recording a video about their experience (6.7%), contacting the influencer directly (3.3%), or deciding not to purchase from that influencer again.

Overall, the data show that most consumers are proactive in expressing their dissatisfaction with influencer-promoted products, primarily through negative reviews and refund requests. Public comments on social media platforms, such as TikTok, are also common.

5.3. Actions to Avoid Getting Scammed or "Budol" in Online Shopping

Figure 5.3 Actions Taken by Respondents to Avoid "Budol" Scams.

Respondents were asked about the actions that consumers should take to avoid becoming victims of "budol" in online shopping. Again, each respondent gave more than one answer. Figure 5.3 showed that fourteen respondents (46%) believe that reading or checking product reviews is crucial for avoiding scams, especially when considering online recommendations. This highlights the value of learning from other customers' experiences before making a purchase.

Six respondents (20%) suggested being cautious and evaluating whether you really need the product or if it might end up being wasted, emphasizing the importance of thoughtful consumption and avoiding impulsive buys based on influencer recommendations. Another six respondents (20%) advised being mindful to prevent impulsive online purchases. Three respondents (10%) recommended verifying the legitimacy of the product to ensure advertisements are authentic. Two

respondents (6.7%) suggested deleting the TikTok app to avoid misleading content, reflecting a cautious approach to social media. Another two (6.7%) advised comparing prices to ensure you're getting good value for your money.

CHAPTER 5

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, and RECOMMENDATIONS

I. SUMMARY

Thirty UPOU senior BAMS students participated in the study, providing their experiences via online surveys distributed through Facebook. The surveys covered demographics, shopping behavior, influencer characteristics, techniques, and consumer experiences. The data was analyzed using quantitative-descriptive methods.

Respondent Demographics

Most respondents (66.7%) are aged 18-22, with 70% being female. The majority are full-time students (73.3%), reflecting a young, predominantly female sample.

Consumer Shopping Behavior

TikTok is a popular shopping platform among respondents, who shop monthly for unique products, fast delivery, and impulse buys. Spending is usually under PHP 200.00, with fashion and clothing being the most common purchases. Interest in categories like food and electronics is lower, likely due to quality concerns.

Influencer Characteristics

1. Characteristics Influencing Consumer Purchases

Respondents value authenticity, reputation, and product knowledge from TikTok influencers. Engaging content and a fun personality also enhance trust,

though attractiveness and sponsorship transparency are less critical.

2. Preferred Influencer's Traits

Respondents place the highest value on authenticity (mean = 4.43), while physical attractiveness is seen as neutral (mean = 3.27). Social media status, expertise, and engaging content are also important, but transparency about sponsorships is considered less significant.

3. Influencer's Characteristics that Deter Purchases

Lack of transparency, negative reputation, and insincerity are major turn-offs, with 70% of respondents identifying these as key deterrents.

4. Impact of Negative Traits of Influencers

Findings indicate that a lack of authenticity and poor product understanding are seen as highly impactful by respondents (means of 3.57 and 3.7) in their purchasing decisions.

Influencer's Techniques

1. Effective Techniques

Demonstrating how a product is used and providing honest reviews are the most persuasive techniques, with 93.3% of respondents finding them effective. Interactive content and limited-time offers are also influential.

2. Ineffective Techniques

Over-promotion (66.7%), generic content (53.3%), and hidden sponsorships (50%) are seen as ineffective. Overly scripted content is particularly disliked (76.7%),

signaling a preference for genuine interactions.

B. Consumer Experience

Online shoppers prioritize price and necessity but also value reviews, recommendations, and product quality. Special deals and algorithm-driven exposure also influence their purchases. When products do not meet expectations, most consumers either leave negative reviews or seek refunds.

To avoid being duped or a victim of budol, respondents recommend reading reviews, avoiding impulsive purchases, verifying product legitimacy, and understanding return procedures.

II. CONCLUSION

The study concludes that authenticity, product knowledge, and engaging content are key drivers of buying behavior, while over-promotion and a lack of transparency deter consumers. The diversity among respondents shows varying perceptions of influencer traits and techniques, though there are some common views.

The study also identifies factors influencing purchasing decisions, such as external recommendations, curiosity, and impulse buying. Common reactions to unmet expectations include leaving negative reviews, requesting refunds, and commenting on the influencer's post.

These insights guide businesses and marketers in refining their strategies and selecting effective influencers, while also helping consumers avoid being duped.

III. Recommendations

For Business Owners

Businesses should collaborate with influencers who are authentic, engaging, and knowledgeable. These qualities are key to building consumer trust and enhancing the effectiveness of marketing efforts.

For TikTok Media Influencers

Consumers favor content that is both entertaining and informative. Influencers should understand their target audience's behavior and preferences to create authentic, relatable content that strengthens connections and drives purchases.

For Consumers

To avoid "budol" schemes, consumers should research and read reviews before making purchases. Awareness of how influencer marketing influences impulse buying can lead to more informed decisions.

For Future Researchers

Future research could expand beyond TikTok to explore the effectiveness of influencer characteristics across different platforms. Additionally, a deeper examination of the consumer decision-making process would provide more comprehensive insights into how influencers impact purchasing decisions.

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